

ROLE OF STAKEHOLDERS AND PERFORMANCE OF SELECTED BARANGAYS IN MARINDUQUE IN THE SEAL OF GOOD LOCAL GOVERNANCE FOR BARANGAYS (SGLGB) PROGRAM: BASIS FOR POLICY INTERVENTION

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ABSTRACT

This study assessed the role of stakeholders and performance of selected barangays in Marinduque in the implementation of the Seal of Good Local Governance for Barangays (SGLGB). It focused on six governance areas: Financial Administration and Sustainability, Disaster Preparedness, Safety, Peace and Order, Social Protection and Sensitivity, Business-Friendliness and Competitiveness, and Environmental Management. Using a quantitative research design, data were gathered through survey questionnaires administered to Punong Barangays, Civil Society Organization Representatives, Municipal LGU Department Heads, and DILG Field Officers. Descriptive statistics were used to analyze performance and stakeholder roles, while Pearson correlation determined their relationship. Findings revealed that barangays performed well in Disaster Preparedness and Business-Friendliness but required improvement in Financial Administration and Environmental Management, particularly in financial reporting, local revenue generation, and waste management. Stakeholders played a key role in financial transparency, community coordination, and policy advocacy, but their influence on barangay performance was statistically weak. Challenges included inadequate financial resources, low community awareness, and lack of training. To address identified gaps, the DILG must institutionalize support mechanisms through technical assistance, performance audits, and a digital monitoring system. Barangays should form compliance teams, conduct regular meetings, and implement improvement

plans. Strengthening stakeholder involvement, enhancing training programs, and promoting public awareness are essential to sustaining effective governance under the SGLGB program. The study recommends that the DILG issue a Memorandum Circular to institutionalize support for barangays through direct technical assistance from Provincial and Field Offices.

Keywords: *Barangay Governance, Seal of Good Local Governance for Barangays (SGLGB), Stakeholder Role, Capacity Building, Local Government Performance*

INTRODUCTION

The performance of barangays in local governance is essential in ensuring the delivery of essential services to their communities. Strong and effective governance at the barangay level contributes to overall local development, accountability, and transparency.

The Department of the Interior and Local Government (DILG) launched the Seal of Good Local Governance for Barangays (SGLGB) Program to encourage and recognize barangays that perform well. It was also introduced to improve the continuous performance of barangays. Further, it was created to ensure accountability, transparency, and participation and to encourage barangays to uphold good governance in Financial Administration and Sustainability, Safety, Peace and Order, Disaster Preparedness, Social Protection and Sensitivity, Business Friendliness and Competitiveness, and Environmental Management. However, the barangays perform differently. Despite the program's objectives, performance results from SGLGB assessments reveal that many barangays still fall short of meeting the required standards. Pilot assessments conducted in recent years have shown that a significant number of barangays in the province of Marinduque, and across the country, struggle with full compliance in several governance areas.

Further, the role of stakeholders in influencing this performance has not been appropriately explored. This research investigates how stakeholder influence affects the performance of selected barangays in Marinduque under the SGLGB Program and proposes policy interventions to enhance performance and stakeholder engagement.

Background of the Study

Local governance is a key component of sustainable development and community empowerment worldwide. United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) framework showed the importance of inclusive and participatory governance at all levels (United Nations, 2015). Different countries have implemented programs to strengthen governance that focus on transparency, accountability, and engagement of stakeholders. Stakeholder theory was initially developed for the private sector and was adapted to the public sector to understand the factors affecting their performance. Different research

shows that stakeholders play a key role in improving the effectiveness of local governance. For example, active stakeholder participation influences the decisions in formulating policies and the delivery of services (Gomes, 2003; Oliveira & Welch, 2013). However, there is still limited research on how local governments perform and what factors influence their effectiveness.

In our country, local governance has been a central focus of public administration reform. The Local Government Code of 1991 provided local government units, including barangays, more freedom and responsibility. The code allowed them to make decisions and manage their resources. (Republic Act No. 7160, 1991). Decentralization was promoted to improve governance by giving barangays more control to address the needs of their community. However, challenges still exist, showing that barangays must continue improving.

The SGLGB Program was introduced to address these challenges by setting criteria and standards. The program assesses the barangays based on financial administration, disaster preparedness, social protection, peace and order, business friendliness and competitiveness, and environmental management. The program recognized barangays who performed beyond their duties and responsibilities. It also provided incentives and support to encourage barangays to improve continuously. Pilot assessments in 2019 and 2021 revealed that only a few barangays had met the standards set by SGLGB. These results highlight ongoing challenges in achieving effective local governance. (DILG, 2019; DILG, 2021). The gaps in the performance of barangays highlight the need to understand the issues and problems they encounter in governance.

In Marinduque, the implementation of the SGLGB Program has shown different results among barangays. Some barangays have performed well. At the same time, other barangays are still having difficulty meeting the required standards. Further, as mentioned by Pagani et al (2015), the success of the SGLGB Program depends on the different roles of stakeholders. The engagement of Stakeholders is crucial for attaining effective governance and improving service delivery (Pagani et al., 2015; Bearfield & Bowman, 2017).

The impact of stakeholders on barangay performance in the SGLGB Program is not yet well understood. While the program aims to improve local governance, barangay performance still varies, showing challenges that need attention. The low passing rates of barangays in pilot assessments show challenges in meeting the standards set in the SGLGB program.

Effective policies can help barangays overcome challenges and improve their performance in the SGLGB program. Formulation of policies will encourage stakeholders to perform their roles and ensure that everyone has a say in barangay officials' decision-making. By promoting collaboration and addressing the challenges, stakeholders can help the SGLGB Program succeed in promoting good governance and better local services.

Research Questions

The study aimed to analyze the role of stakeholders and performance of selected barangays in Marinduque in the implementation of the Seal of Good Local Governance for Barangays (SGLGB).

Specifically, the research sought to answer the following:

1. What is the current level of performance of selected barangays in Marinduque in the SGLGB program in terms of:
 - 1.1. Financial Administration and Sustainability
 - 1.2. Disaster Preparedness
 - 1.3. Safety, Peace, and Order
 - 1.4. Social Protection and Sensitivity
 - 1.5. Business Friendliness and Competitiveness
 - 1.6. Environmental Management
2. What is the role of stakeholders in the implementation of the SGLGB program in the selected barangays in terms of:
 - 2.1. Financial Administration and Sustainability
 - 2.1.1. Municipal LGU
 - 2.1.2. Civil Society Organization
 - 2.1.3. Municipal Local Government Operations Officer (MLGOO)
 - 2.2. Disaster Preparedness
 - 2.2.1. Municipal LGU
 - 2.2.2. Civil Society Organization
 - 2.2.3. Municipal Local Government Operations Officer (MLGOO)
 - 2.3. Safety, Peace, and Order
 - 2.3.1. Municipal LGU
 - 2.3.2. Civil Society Organization
 - 2.3.3. Municipal Local Government Operations Officer (MLGOO)
 - 2.4. Social Protection and Sensitivity
 - 2.4.1. Municipal LGU
 - 2.4.2. Civil Society Organization
 - 2.4.3. Municipal Local Government Operations Officer (MLGOO)
 - 2.5. Business Friendliness and Competitiveness
 - 2.5.1. Municipal LGU
 - 2.5.2. Civil Society Organization
 - 2.5.3. Municipal Local Government Operations Officer (MLGOO)
 - 2.6. Environmental Management
 - 2.6.1. Municipal LGU
 - 2.6.2. Civil Society Organization
 - 2.6.3. Municipal Local Government Operations Officer (MLGOO)
3. Is there a significant relationship between the role of stakeholders and the performance of the barangays in the SGLGB program?
4. What are the challenges that affect the performance of selected barangays and the role of stakeholders in the SGLGB program?

5. What strategies could be implemented to improve the performance of barangays and the role of stakeholders in the SGLGB program?
6. What possible policy interventions can be formulated to address the gap identified in the study?

METHODOLOGY

This study utilized a quantitative-descriptive research design to examine the performance of selected barangays under the Seal of Good Local Governance for Barangays (SGLGB) Program and the role of stakeholders in improving barangay governance. The research was conducted in the province of Marinduque composed of six municipalities. This province was selected as the locale of the study due to its diversity in terms of governance performance and the presence of both urbanizing and rural barangays, which makes it representative of typical local government conditions in the Philippines.

To determine the number of barangays included in the sample, Slovin's formula was used with a 5% margin of error. From a total of 218 barangays in the province, a sample of 141 barangays was selected. Proportional allocation was used to distribute the barangays among the six municipalities, and a random selection tool was employed to ensure unbiased inclusion. Respondents in the study included 141 Punong Barangays, 141 civil society organizations representatives, 38 municipal department heads involved in the implementation of the SGLGB program, and six field officers from the six municipalities, bringing the total number of respondents to 326. The respondents' demographic data were not collected, as the primary focus of the study was on their governance roles and performance metrics rather than personal characteristics.

The data gathering process involved two key instruments. First, the study used a modified SGLGB assessment data retrieval tool to obtain performance data of barangays based on the official SGLGB assessment conducted by DILG. This tool provided quantitative results, including percentage scores and adjectival ratings across the six governance areas. Second, a researcher-made questionnaire was designed and administered to assess stakeholder roles, identify challenges, and gather suggestions for enhancing governance. The questionnaire was reviewed and validated by five experts in the field such as local government operations officers and program manager. The instrument was rated highly in terms of relevance, clarity, and utility, with an average score of 5 in all evaluated aspects except one, where it scored 4, indicating strong content validity.

Formal letters were sent to local authorities to request permission to collect data from barangays and use SGLGB results. After receiving approval, the researcher distributed the questionnaires directly to the identified respondents. Coordination with municipal officials and field officers ensured smooth administration and retrieval of the completed forms.

The analysis of data was conducted using both descriptive and inferential statistical tools. Weighted mean was used to assess barangay performance and stakeholder roles, while frequency and percentage analyses were applied to evaluate challenges and suggested strategies. To determine whether there was a significant relationship between the role of stakeholders and barangay performance, the Pearson Product-Moment Correlation Coefficient was computed using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) software.

This study was limited to barangays within one province and focused exclusively on the SGLGB 2023 assessment cycle. As such, findings may not be generalized to all barangays nationwide. Moreover, while the study examined stakeholder involvement, it did not measure all external factors that might influence barangay performance, such as political dynamics or socioeconomic disparities. Nonetheless, the results provide valuable insights into stakeholder engagement and its influence on governance outcomes, serving as a basis for future policy interventions aimed at strengthening the SGLGB program implementation.

RESULTS

Part I. Level of Performance of Selected Barangays in Marinduque in the SGLGB program in terms of:

Table 1
Financial Administration and Sustainability

Indicators	Performance Score							Overall	Adjectival Rating
	Boac	Buena vista	Gasan	Mogpog	Santa Cruz	Torrijos			
1.1 Compliance with the Barangay Full Disclosure Policy (BFDP) Board	Posted the CY 2023 financial documents in the BFDP board	100.00	100.00	100.00	62.50	100.00	100.00	93.62	Outstanding
	Accomplished prescribed BFR form	7.50	80.00	100.00	25.00	25.71	68.75	37.59	Needs Improvement
1.2 Innovations on Revenue Generation or Exercise of Corporate Powers	Increase in local resources in 2023	42.50	30.00	50.00	37.50	42.86	37.50	41.13	Needs Improvement
1.3 Approval of the Barangay Budget on the Specified Timeframe	Presence of a Barangay Appropriation Ordinance approved on or before December 31, 2022	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	93.75	99.29	Outstanding

1.4 Allocation for Statutory Programs and Projects as Mandated by Laws and/or Other Issuances	With allocated funds for the statutory programs and projects	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	87.50	98.58	Outstanding
1.5 Posting of the Barangay Citizen's Charter (CITCHA)	Barangay Citizens' Charter posted at a conspicuous place	100.00	80.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	75.00	95.74	Outstanding
1.6 Release of the Sangguniang Kabataan (SK) Funds of the Barangay	Compliance with Section 20 of the SK Reform Act of 2015	100.00	90.00	100.00	100.00	68.57	93.75	90.78	Outstanding
	Presence of Annual Barangay Youth Investment Program (ABYIP)	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	Outstanding
1.7 Conduct of Barangay Assembly for CY 2022 (2nd Semester)	Conducted Barangay Assembly	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	81.25	97.87	Outstanding
Average Performance Score		83.33	86.67	94.44	80.56	81.90	81.94	83.85	Very Good

Table 2
Disaster Preparedness

Indicators	Performance Score							Overall	Adjectival Rating
	Boac	Buena vista	Gasan	Mogpog	Santa Cruz	Torrijos			
2.1 Functionality of the Barangay Disaster Risk Reduction and Management Committee (BDRRMC)	Established BDRRMC with its composition-compliant	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	93.75	99.29	Outstanding
	Approved Barangay Disaster Risk Reduction and Management (BDRRM) Plan	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	93.75	99.29	Outstanding
	Allocation of 5% of the Estimated Revenue from Regular Sources as	100.00	100.00	100.00	62.50	97.14	100.00	92.91	Outstanding

	BDRRM Fund									
	At least 50% accomplishment of the physical or financial targets	100.00	100.00	93.75	50.00	45.71	93.75	76.60		Good
2.2 Extent of Risk Assessment and Early Warning System (EWS)	Conducted an activity in relation to Risk Assessment in the barangay	100.00	100.00	93.75	62.50	100.00	43.75	86.52		Very Good
	A certified Barangay Risk/Hazard Map	100.00	100.00	93.75	62.50	100.00	68.75	89.36		Very Good
	An established Early Warning System for the top two (2) hazards present in the barangay	100.00	100.00	93.75	62.50	100.00	68.75	89.36		Very Good
2.3 Extent of Preparedness for Effective Response and Recovery	A permanent or alternate evacuation center	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00		Outstanding
	Have the basic disaster supplies/equipment	100.00	100.00	56.25	100.00	100.00	56.25	90.07		Outstanding
	Average Performance Score	100.00	100.00	92.36	77.78	93.65	79.86	91.49		Outstanding

Table 3
Safety, Peace, and Order

Indicators	Performance Score							Overall	Adjectival Rating
	Boac	Buena vista	Gasán	Mogpog	Santa Cruz	Torrijos			
3.1 Functionality of the Barangay Anti-Drug Abuse Council (BADAC)	Organized BADAC with its composition and appropriate committees	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	Outstanding
	Established a Rehabilitation Referral Desk with a Designated Duty Officer	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	93.75	99.29	Outstanding

	Organized House Clusters with designated House Cluster Leaders (HCL)	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	75.00	97.16	Outstanding
	Organized BADAC Auxiliary Team (BAT)	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	93.75	99.29	Outstanding
	Approved BADAC Plan of Action	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	Outstanding
	Allocation of a substantial amount for anti-illegal drugs initiative	20.00	100.00	100.00	45.83	11.43	100.00	46.10	Needs Improvement
	Organized at least 1 community-based IEC Activity during CY 2023	100.00	90.00	100.00	100.00	11.43	100.00	77.30	Good
	Submitted Consolidated Information Report (CIR) to CADAC/MA DAC and Local PNP Unit	100.00	100.00	100.00	33.33	100.00	93.75	87.94	Very Good
	Implemented Community-Based Intervention for PWUDs	100.00	0.00	12.50	95.83	85.71	43.75	72.34	Good
	Conducted at least 3 Monthly Meetings	100.00	30.00	12.50	54.17	11.43	93.75	54.61	Needs Improvement
3.2	Functionality of the Barangay Peace and Order Committee (BPOC)								
	Organized BPOC with its composition compliant with the provisions of EO 366	100.00	100.00	100.00	62.50	100.00	100.00	93.62	Outstanding
	Approved Barangay Peace and Order and Public Safety (BPOPS) Plan	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	Outstanding

	At least 50% accomplishment of the physical or financial targets	100.00	100.00	100.00	54.17	100.00	100.00	92.20	Outstanding
3.3 Functionality of the Lupong Tagapamayapa (LT)	Organized Lupong Tagapamayapa with at least 10 members	100.00	100.00	93.75	100.00	22.86	62.50	75.89	Good
	Systematic maintenance of records of cases	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	75.00	97.16	Outstanding
	Conducted at least 3 monthly meetings for the administration of the Katarungang Pambarangay	100.00	30.00	50.00	45.83	20.00	31.25	52.48	Needs Improvement
	Attendance of LT to KP training or seminar	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	56.25	95.04	Outstanding
3.4 Organization and Strengthening Capacities of Barangay Tanod	Organized Barangay Tanod	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	93.75	99.29	Outstanding
	Attendance of barangay "tanod" to necessary training	100.00	100.00	100.00	62.50	100.00	56.25	88.65	Very Good
3.5 Barangay Initiatives during Health Emergencies	Organized Barangay Health and Emergency Response Team (BHERT)	100.00	100.00	100.00	66.67	100.00	75.00	91.49	Outstanding
	Poster or tarpaulin containing the active Numbers of the BHERT Members	100.00	100.00	100.00	66.67	100.00	56.25	89.36	Very Good
3.6 Conduct of Monthly Barangay Road Clearing Operations (BARCO)	Conducted at least 3 BaRCO on a monthly basis	100.00	100.00	93.75	75.00	100.00	37.50	87.94	Very Good
Average Performance Score		96.36	88.64	89.20	80.11	80.13	78.98	86.23	Very Good

Table 4
Social Protection and Sensitivity

Indicators		Performance Score							Adjectival Rating
		Boac	Buena vista	Gasán	Mogpog	Santa Cruz	Torrijos	Overall	
4.1 Functionality of Barangay Violence Against Women (VAW) Desk	Established Barangay VAW Desk and designated Barangay VAW Desk Officer	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	87.50	98.58	Outstanding
	Attendance of the Barangay VAW Desk Officer to at least one (1) training/orientation	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	37.50	92.91	Outstanding
	Approved 2023 Barangay Gender and Development (GAD) Plan and Budget	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	Outstanding
	Submission of Monthly Accomplishment Reports on the incidence of VAW and VAC	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	31.25	92.20	Outstanding
	Updated database on VAW cases reported to the barangay	100.00	100.00	93.75	100.00	100.00	75.00	96.45	Outstanding
	At least 50% accomplishment of the physical or financial targets	100.00	80.00	100.00	50.00	60.00	25.00	71.63	Good
	4.2 Access to Health and Social Welfare Services in the Barangay	Presence of a Barangay Health Station/Center	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	93.75	99.29
	Appointment of a Barangay Health Worker (BHW)	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	Outstanding
	Appointment of a Barangay	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	93.75	99.29	Outstanding

	Nutrition Scholar (BNS)									
	Availability of the basic health services in the BHS/C	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	93.75	99.29	Outstanding	
4.3	Functionality of the Barangay Development Council (BDC)									
	Organized BDC with its composition compliant to Section 107 of RA 7160	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	81.25	97.87	Outstanding	
	Conducted public hearings/ barangay assemblies for public consultation	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	56.25	95.04	Outstanding	
	Approved Barangay Development Plan	100.00	80.00	100.00	37.50	100.00	81.25	85.82	Very Good	
	At least 50% accomplishment of the physical or financial targets	100.00	100.00	100.00	29.17	34.29	12.50	61.70	Poor	
4.4	Implementation of the Kasambahay Law									
	Kasambahay Desk with designated Kasambahay Desk Officer (KDO)	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	75.00	97.16	Outstanding	
	Maintenance /updating of a Kasambahay Masterlist	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	50.00	94.33	Outstanding	
4.5	Functionality of the Barangay Council for the Protection of Children (BCPC)									
	Organization of the Barangay Council for Protection of Children (BCPC)	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	Outstanding	
	Attendance of the Members of the (BCPC) to at least one (1) training/orientation	2.50	50.00	31.25	100.00	100.00	100.00	60.99	Poor	
	Approved BCPC Annual Work and	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	75.00	96.16	Outstanding	

	Financial Plan								
	Database on Children disaggregated by age, sex, ethnicity, with or with disabilities, OSCY, etc.	100.00	100.00	93.75	100.00	100.00	56.25	94.33	Outstanding
	Updated Localized Flow Chart of Referral System	100.00	50.00	93.75	100.00	82.86	100.00	91.49	Outstanding
	At least 50% completion or utilization rate on PPAs	100.00	100.00	93.75	50.00	11.43	93.75	68.09	Poor
4.6 Mechanism for Gender and Development (GAD)	Organized Barangay GAD Focal Point System	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	81.25	97.87	Outstanding
4.7 Maintenance of Updated Record of Barangay Inhabitants (RBIS)	Updated RBI for two semesters	100.00	100.00	93.75	54.17	100.00	68.75	87.94	Very Good
4.8 Functionality of the Barangay Nutrition Committee (BNC)	Organization of the Barangay Nutrition Committee (BNC)	100.00	100.00	100.00	62.50	100.00	81.25	91.49	Outstanding
	Presence of Barangay Nutrition Action Plan (BNAP)	100.00	100.00	93.75	100.00	100.00	81.25	97.16	Outstanding
	Decrease in Malnutrition Rate in the barangay	37.50	10.00	100.00	83.33	62.86	75.00	60.99	Needs Improvement
	At least 50% accomplishment of the physical or financial targets	100.00	90.00	100.00	37.50	100.00	18.75	79.43	Good
	Average Performance Score	94.29	91.43	96.21	85.86	91.12	72.32	89.59	Very Good

Table 5
Business-Friendliness and Competitiveness

Indicators		Performance Score							Adjectival Rating
		Boac	Buena vista	Gasán	Mogpog	Santa Cruz	Torrijos	Overall	
5.1 Power to Levy Other Taxes, Fees, or Charges	Enacted Barangay Tax Ordinance pursuant to Sec. 129 of the LGC	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	81.25	97.87	Outstanding
5.2 Compliance to Section 11 of RA 11032 or the Ease of Doing Business	Enacted Barangay Ordinance relative to Barangay Clearance fees on business permit and locational clearance	100.00	90.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	81.25	97.16	Outstanding
	Approved resolution authorizing the City/Municipal Treasurer to collect fees for Barangay Clearance for Business permit and locational clearance	100.00	20.00	100.00	100.00	17.14	81.25	71.63	Good
5.3 Issuance of Barangay Clearance not covered by DILG MC No. 2019-177	Presence of a Citizens' Charter on the issuance of barangay clearance posted in the barangay hall	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	50.00	94.33	Outstanding
Average Passing Rate		100.00	77.50	100.00	100.00	79.29	73.44	90.25	Outstanding

Table 6
Environmental Management

Indicators		Performance Score							Adjectival Rating
		Boac	Buena vista	Gasán	Mogpog	Santa Cruz	Torrijos	Overall	
6.1 Functionality of the Barangay Ecological	Organized BESWMC with composition compliant to	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	93.75	99.29	Outstanding

Solid Waste Management Committee (BESWMC)	DILG MC No. 2018-112									
	Approved Solid Waste Management Program/Plan with corresponding fund allocation	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	87.50	98.58	Outstanding	
	Attendance of BESWMC to necessary training	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	17.14	62.50	75.18	Good	
	At least 50% completion or utilization rate on PPAs	100.00	100.00	100.00	29.17	0.00	50.00	57.45	Needs Improvement	
6.2 Existence of a Solid Waste Management Facility pursuant to R.A. 9003	Presence of a Materials Recovery Facility (MRF)/ Materials Recovery System (MRS)	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	Outstanding	
6.3 Provision of Support Mechanisms for Segregated Collection	Enacted Barangay Ordinance or similar issuance on segregation of wastes at-source	30.00	40.00	100.00	100.00	14.29	81.25	52.48	Needs Improvement	
Average Passing Rate		88.33	90.00	100.00	88.19	55.24	79.17	80.50	Very Good	

Part II. Role of Stakeholders in the Implementation of the SGLGB Program in the Selected Barangays in Terms of:

Table 7
Financial Administration and Sustainability

Role of Stakeholders	Weighted Mean				Interpretation	Rank
	CSOs	Municipal LGU	MLGOO	Overall mean		
Capacity-Building Providers	3.2340	3.1667	3.6667	3.2350	Effective	1
Financial Oversight Partners	3.1418	3.2778	3.8333	3.1913	Effective	2
Technical Experts	3.1631	3.1944	3.5000	3.1803	Effective	3

Participatory Budgeting Contributors	3.1631	3.1667	3.5000	3.1749	Effective	4
Ethical and Moral Advocates	3.1135	3.1667	3.5000	3.1366	Effective	5
Decision-Making Partners	3.1348	3.0000	3.5000	3.1202	Effective	6
Project Funders	3.1206	3.1111	3.1667	3.1202	Effective	6
Research and Policy Consultants	3.1489	2.9722	3.1667	3.1148	Effective	8
Financial Strategy Partners	3.1064	3.1389	3.1667	3.1148	Effective	8
Equity Advocates	3.0922	3.1944	3.000	3.1093	Effective	10
Resource Allocation Influencers	3.0851	3.1389	3.000	3.0929	Effective	11
Policy Advisors	3.0851	3.0833	3.333	3.0929	Effective	11
Infrastructure Investment Partners	3.1773	2.7500	3.000	3.0874	Effective	13
Grand Mean	3.1358	3.1047	3.3333	3.1362	Effective	

Table 8
Disaster Preparedness

Role of Stakeholders	Weighted Mean				Interpretation	Rank
	CSOs	Municipal LGU	MLGOO	Overall mean		
Community Coordinators	3.1773	3.3889	3.6667	3.2350	Effective	1
Community Mobilizers	3.1773	3.3056	3.6667	3.2186	Effective	2
Interagency Coordinators	3.1773	3.3056	3.5000	3.2131	Effective	3
Public Awareness Advocates	3.1773	3.3056	3.3333	3.2077	Effective	4
Policy Developers	3.1702	3.1667	3.6667	3.1858	Effective	5

First Responders	3.1418	3.1389	3.5000	3.1530	Effective	6
Logistical Support Providers	3.1135	3.2222	3.6667	3.1530	Effective	6
Funding Supporters	3.0922	3.2778	3.1667	3.1311	Effective	8
Risk Reduction Planners	3.0922	3.2222	3.5000	3.1311	Effective	8
Research and Risk Analysts	3.0922	3.1111	3.3333	3.1038	Effective	10
Grand Mean	3.1411	3.2444	3.5000	3.1732	Effective	

Table 9
Safety, Peace and Order

Role of Stakeholders	Weighted Mean				Interpretation	Rank
	CSOs	Municipal LGU	MLGOO	Overall mean		
Community Watch Partners	3.1560	3.2778	3.6667	3.1967	Effective	1
Collaborators in Social Program Implementation	3.1418	3.3056	3.6667	3.1913	Effective	2
Community Project Supporters	3.1489	3.2778	3.6667	3.1913	Effective	2
Accountability and Human Rights Monitors	3.1206	3.2500	3.6667	3.1639	Effective	4
Peace Education Providers	3.1418	3.1389	3.6667	3.1585	Effective	5
Peace and Order Monitors	3.1348	3.0833	3.8333	3.1475	Effective	6
Local Governance Supporters	3.0993	3.2500	3.6667	3.1475	Effective	6
Governance Process Participants	3.0922	3.2222	3.6667	3.1366	Effective	8
Law Adherence Advocates	3.0922	3.1944	3.8333	3.1366	Effective	8

Funding and Logistical Support Providers	3.1489	3.0278	3.5000	3.1366	Effective	8
Grand Mean	3.1277	3.2028	3.6833	3.1607	Effective	

Table 10
Social Protection and Sensitivity

Role of Stakeholders	Weighted Mean				Interpretation	Rank
	CSOs	Municipal LGU	MLGOO	Overall mean		
Community Initiative Participants	3.1986	3.2778	3.3333	3.2186	Effective	1
Abuse and Neglect Reporters	3.2057	3.2500	3.1667	3.2131	Effective	2
Social Welfare Collaborators	3.1489	3.3611	3.1667	3.1913	Effective	3
Program Oversight Partners	3.1631	3.2222	3.5000	3.1858	Effective	4
Awareness Campaign Advocates	3.1418	3.3333	3.3333	3.1858	Effective	4
Representation Advocates	3.1135	3.2778	3.5000	3.1585	Effective	6
Social Inclusion Trainers	3.1348	3.1944	3.3333	3.1530	Effective	7
Rights Advocates for Marginalized Communities	3.1206	3.1944	3.6667	3.1530	Effective	7
Policy Enforcers for Social Protection	3.1631	3.0000	3.6667	3.1475	Effective	9
Community Initiative Leaders	3.1064	3.2778	3.1667	3.1421	Effective	10
Resource Allocators for Social Programs	3.1348	3.1667	3.0000	3.1366	Effective	11

Grand Mean	3.1483	3.2323	3.3485	3.1714	Effective
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Table 11
Business Friendliness and Competitiveness

Role of Stakeholders	Weighted Mean				Interpretation	Rank
	CSOs	Municipal LGU	MLGOO	Overall mean		
Economic Research Providers	3.2411	3.1111	3.3333	3.2186	Effective	1
Development Initiative Participants	3.1702	3.1944	3.5000	3.1858	Effective	2
Policy Framework Developers	3.2270	3.0278	3.1667	3.1858	Effective	2
Business Supporters	3.1560	3.1111	3.6667	3.1639	Effective	4
Policy Reform Advocates	3.1418	3.0278	3.3333	3.1257	Effective	5
Financial and Technical Assistance Providers	3.1631	2.9722	3.1667	3.1257	Effective	6
Public-Private Partnership Collaborators	3.0851	3.0278	2.8333	3.0656	Effective	7
Entrepreneurial Capacity Builders	3.1702	2.9167	3.1667	3.1202	Effective	8
Local Investors and Job Creators	3.0993	3.0833	3.0000	3.0929	Effective	8
Business Development Service Providers	3.0851	3.0833	3.5000	3.0984	Effective	10
Grand Mean	3.1539	3.0556	3.2667	3.1383	Effective	

Table 12
Environmental Management

Role of Stakeholders	Weighted Mean				Interpretation	Rank
	CSOs	Municipal LGU	MLGOO	Overall mean		
Environmental Reporters	3.2057	3.2222	3.1667	3.2077	Effective	1
Environmental Researchers	3.2553	3.0000	3.3333	3.2077	Effective	1
Environmental Educators	3.1702	3.1667	3.6667	3.1858	Effective	3
Policy Advocates for the Environment	3.1844	3.1389	3.3333	3.1803	Effective	4
Conservation Activity Participants	3.1418	3.1944	3.6667	3.1694	Effective	5
Regulation Enforcers	3.1844	3.0000	3.3333	3.1530	Effective	6
Environmental Assistance Providers	3.1773	3.0556	3.1667	3.1530	Effective	6
Resource Allocators for Environmental Projects	3.1064	3.2778	3.0000	3.1366	Effective	8
Environmental Partnership Builders	3.1418	3.1111	3.1667	3.1366	Effective	8
Environmental Regulation Developers	3.1206	3.1111	3.1667	3.1202	Effective	10
Grand Mean	3.1688	3.1278	3.3000	3.1650	Effective	

Part III. Significant Relationship between the Role of Stakeholders and the Performance of the Barangays in the SGLGB Program

Table 13

Correlation between Role of Stakeholders and Level of Performance in SGLGB

Governance Areas	Civil Society Organization		Municipal LGU		DILG MLGOO	
	Pearson Correlation	Interpretation	Pearson Correlation	Interpretation	Pearson Correlation	Interpretation
Financial Administration	-0.122	Weak negative correlation	-0.132	Weak negative correlation	0.680	Moderate positive correlation
Disaster Preparedness	0.324	Weak positive correlation	0.111	Weak positive correlation	0.404	Moderate positive correlation
Safety, Peace and Order	0.071	Weak positive correlation	-0.006	Weak negative correlation	0.534	Moderate positive correlation
Social Protection and Sensitivity	0.196	Weak positive correlation	0.075	Weak positive correlation	0.376	Weak positive correlation
Business Friendliness and Competitiveness	0.118	Weak positive correlation	0.097	Weak positive correlation	0.187	Weak positive correlation
Environmental Management	-0.216	Weak negative correlation	-0.096	Weak negative correlation	0.625	Moderate positive correlation

Part IV. Challenges that Affect the Performance of Selected Barangays in the SGLGB program and the Role of Stakeholders

Table 14

Challenges that affect the performance of selected barangays in the SGLGB program

Challenges	Mean	Interpretation	Rank
Barangays face difficulties due to inadequate financial resources for implementing SGLGB Program activities.	3.1481	Agree	1
There is a lack of community awareness and engagement in SGLGB Program initiatives.	3.0957	Agree	2

There is a lack of trained personnel to manage and execute the SGLGB Program effectively in the barangays.	3.0802	Agree	3
Poor infrastructure in barangays hampers the achievement of SGLGB Program goals.	3.0802	Agree	3
Challenges related to disaster preparedness and management affect barangay performance in the SGLGB Program.	3.0741	Agree	4
Political interference affects the impartial implementation of the SGLGB Program in the barangays.	3.0617	Agree	5
Conflicts between barangay officials and community members negatively impact the effectiveness of the SGLGB Program.	3.0556	Agree	6
Limited access to information and resources for barangay officials affects their ability to meet SGLGB Program requirements.	3.0494	Agree	7
Bureaucratic red tape and administrative delays affect the timely implementation of the SGLGB Program.	3.0309	Agree	8
Insufficient support from local government units impedes barangay performance in the SGLGB Program.	2.9599	Agree	9
Grand Mean	3.0636	Agree	

Table 15

Challenges that affect the role of stakeholders in the SGLGB program

Challenges	Mean	Interpretation	Rank
Stakeholders experience challenges in understanding the requirements and processes of the SGLGB Program.	3.0741	Agree	1
Stakeholders face challenges in mobilizing community support for SGLGB Program initiatives.	3.0679	Agree	2
There is a lack of training and capacity-building opportunities for stakeholders involved in the SGLGB Program.	3.0401	Agree	3
Stakeholders experience difficulties in providing constructive feedback for the improvement of the SGLGB Program.	3.0370	Agree	4

Political or personal conflicts among stakeholders and barangay officials hinder collaborative efforts in the SGLGB Program.	3.0340	Agree	5
Stakeholders face difficulties in establishing effective communication with barangay officials.	3.0154	Agree	6
There are insufficient resources allocated to stakeholders for their involvement in the SGLGB Program.	3.0093	Agree	7
Stakeholders face barriers due to limited access to information about the SGLGB Program's objectives and activities.	3.0031	Agree	8
There is a lack of coordination among stakeholders, which affects the effectiveness of the SGLGB Program.	2.9938	Agree	9
Stakeholders are often not included in the decision-making processes related to the SGLGB Program.	2.9907	Agree	10
Grand Mean	3.0265	Agree	

Part V. Strategies to Improve the Performance of Barangays in the SGLGB Program

Table 16

DILG initiated strategies to improve the performance of barangays in the SGLGB program

DILG Initiated Strategies	Percentage	Rank
Conduct workshops for barangay officials on governance, financial management, and accountability.	89.30%	1
Create a digital platform for real-time monitoring of barangay performance and SGLGB compliance.	74.90%	2
Develop a training program for barangay officials.	74.60%	3
Conduct an information education campaign to educate communities about the SGLGB program.	72.20%	4
Facilitate workshops for barangays to share best practices and collaborate on joint projects.	69.70%	5
Establish a support center to provide technical assistance and guidance to barangays on SGLGB compliance.	60.20%	6

Create and distribute a comprehensive guide on SGLGB requirements and best practices.	60.20%	6
Introduce a benchmarking system to compare and improve barangay practices based on successful models.	58.70%	7
Collaborate with States and Universities to provide research and analysis on improving barangay performance.	50.50%	8

Table 17

Barangay initiated strategies to improve the performance of barangays in the SGLGB program

Barangay Initiated Strategies	Percentage	Rank
Create an SGLGB team that would spearhead the monitoring of compliances in the SGLGB program.	77.50%	1
Hold monthly meetings to discuss the requirements of SGLGB.	72.00%	2
Organize forums every quarter for residents to provide feedback and discuss improvements.	64.60%	3
Develop a barangay performance improvement plan based on feedback and audit results.	63.70%	4
Establish partnerships with stakeholders to support barangay projects and activities.	59.70%	5
Implement a barangay-level performance review process to assess progress and address challenges.	54.70%	6
Conduct an audit to identify and optimize resource use, focusing on procurement and infrastructure maintenance.	52.60%	7
Launch a community-driven initiative to promote active participation in barangay governance.	51.10%	8
Form councils with neighboring barangays to discuss and collaborate on shared projects and issues.	49.80%	9
Install suggestion boxes in public areas and create online forms for residents to submit feedback.	48.90%	10

DISCUSSION

Part I. Level of Performance of Selected Barangays in Marinduque in the SGLGB program in terms of:

Financial Administration and Sustainability

Table 1 shows that the performance of selected barangays in Financial Administration and Sustainability is rated very good, with a passing rate of 83.85. The data shows that barangays are committed to fiscal accountability, transparency, and efficiency. Gisselquist (2014) highlighted in his study that financial transparency and accountability are essential to good governance. Transparency and accountability encourage citizen participation and enhance service delivery. Barangays also demonstrated high performance in individual indicators. In compliance with the Barangay Full Disclosure Policy (BFDP) Board, they achieved an outstanding rating of 93.62. However, the Accomplished Barangay Financial Report (BFR) indicator received a low passing rate of only 37.59%. Most barangays could not submit their financial reports to the Municipal Accounting Office. Hence, this highlights the challenge barangays face in complying with financial reporting requirements.

Regarding innovations in revenue generation or exercise of corporate power, barangays received a low score of 41.13%, indicating a need for improvement. This rating suggests that most barangays did not experience an increase in their local revenue resources. Barangays demonstrated exemplary performance in approving the barangay budget within the specified timeframe and allocating statutory programs and projects as mandated by laws and other issuances, achieving outstanding ratings (99.29 and 98.58, respectively). Similarly, they performed well in posting the Barangay Citizen's Charter (CITCHA) in conspicuous places and conducting the barangay assembly day, receiving an adjectival rating of "outstanding." In terms of the release of Sangguniang Kabataan (SK) funds, barangays achieved the highest rating of 100 for the presence of the Annual Barangay Youth Investment Program (ABYIP) while attaining a passing rate of 90.78%, or "outstanding," in compliance with Section 20 of the SK Reform Act of 2015, which mandates the transfer of funds to Sangguniang Kabataan accounts. The lowest scores in submitting the accomplished prescribed Barangay Financial Report (BFR) form and the increase in local revenue resources indicators show the need for capacity-building initiatives. Brillantes (2001) highlighted that providing capacity intervention will enhance financial management and ensure compliance with reporting requirements.

Further analysis of Table 1 shows varying levels of performance across the six municipalities. Among them, Gasan attained the highest overall average passing rate of 94.44%, demonstrating exceptional compliance in most indicators, including perfect scores in the accomplishment of the prescribed BFR form, timely approval of the barangay budget, and full implementation of youth-related programs such as ABYIP. This suggests that Gasan barangays have established strong financial systems and are effectively implementing budgetary and administrative mandates.

Buenavista followed with a passing rate of 86.67%, exhibiting solid performance in nearly all indicators, particularly in compliance with the BFDP Board and the timely release of SK funds. The high score in the accomplished BFR form (80%) reflects efforts toward improving financial documentation, though there is still room for improvement compared to the standard.

Boac, with an average passing rate of 83.33%, performed well overall but notably scored very low (7.50%) in the submission of the BFR form, which significantly pulled down its overall performance. Despite this, Boac achieved high scores in other areas such as the timely approval of the budget and allocation for statutory programs.

Torrijos and Santa Cruz were close in performance, scoring 81.94% and 81.90%, respectively. These municipalities showed consistency in compliance with high-priority indicators like budget approval, SK fund release, and citizen's charter posting. However, they also underperformed in indicators like submission of BFR and local resource generation, suggesting the need for technical support in financial reporting and revenue enhancement.

Mogpog, meanwhile, recorded the lowest average passing rate at 80.56%. While it achieved outstanding ratings in many core compliance indicators, its score in BFR accomplishment (25%) and local revenue increase (37.5%) points to a significant need for capacity-building and technical support. This underlines a gap in back-end financial management, which may affect the sustainability of service delivery and project implementation.

Overall, the analysis reveals that while most barangays across all municipalities are meeting basic compliance requirements under the SGLGB program, their effectiveness in financial documentation and revenue enhancement remains inconsistent. The consistently low scores in BFR submission and local resource generation across municipalities suggest a systemic issue that could be addressed through enhanced training, closer supervision, and digital solutions to streamline financial reporting processes.

Disaster Preparedness

Table 2 presents the performance in disaster preparedness with an outstanding rating of 91.49. Barangays ensure the safety of their respective communities against natural and man-made disasters.

Barangays performed well on the first indicator, the functionality of the Barangay Disaster Risk Reduction and Management Committee (BDRRMC), by complying with the requirements for establishing the council (99.29), formulating and approving the Barangay Disaster Risk Reduction and Management (BDRRM) Plan (99.29), and allocating 5% of the estimated revenue from regular sources as the BDRRM Fund (92.91).

However, barangays attained only a "good" rating of 76.60 in accomplishing the BDRRM physical and financial targets, indicating gaps in program implementation.

Although barangays allocated budgetary resources for programs, projects, and activities under the BDRRM Fund, they encountered challenges during implementation. Capuno et al. (2001) highlight in their study that a strong monitoring mechanism is necessary to utilize allocated funds properly. Hence, there is a need to fully implement the programs, projects, and activities outlined in the BDRRM Plan.

Barangays attained a "very good" rating in the indicator for risk assessment and early warning systems. They received a rating of 86.52 for conducting activities related to risk assessment, 89.36 for ensuring the presence of a certified Barangay Risk or Hazard Map, and 89.36 for establishing an early warning system for the top two hazards in their respective barangays. Barangays are committed to establishing risk assessment and early warning systems crucial for disaster preparedness. However, there is room for improvement to enhance performance in these areas. Barangays achieved an "outstanding" rating in the indicator for preparedness for effective response and recovery. Barangays received a perfect score of 100 for establishing permanent or alternate evacuation centres and a rating of 90.07 for ensuring their barangays have basic supplies and equipment for disasters. Showing that barangays have prioritized preparedness, response, and recovery. As highlighted by Cagas and Balacy (2022), infrastructure and resources play a vital role in ensuring the safety of people during disasters.

Further analysis of Table 2 shows varying levels of performance. Boac and Buenavista both achieved a perfect 100% average performance score. The result indicates that the barangays in these municipalities fully complied with the disaster preparedness indicators under the SGLGB program. These barangays showed strong performance across all areas, including the establishment of BDRRMCs, approval of BDRRM plans, allocation of the 5% DRRM fund, and presence of risk assessment systems. Their perfect scores in preparedness for response and recovery reflect a high level of readiness.

Santa Cruz also performed very well with an average score of 93.65%. It met most of the indicators at an outstanding level, particularly in organizing its BDRRMC and preparing its DRRM plans. However, it slightly lagged in the area of accomplishing physical and financial targets under the BDRRM Plan, scoring only 45.71%, and in the availability of basic disaster supplies and equipment, where it scored 100%, though its overall average in other indicators brought down its total slightly compared to Boac and Buenavista. This suggests that while planning and structures are present, execution and follow-through on DRRM-related programs may need closer monitoring and stronger implementation support.

Gasán, with an average of 92.36%, also demonstrated strong performance but showed minor gaps in equipment readiness and plan execution. Meanwhile, Mogpog and Torrijos had notably lower performance scores with 77.78% and 79.86% respectively. The result is mainly due to low marks in risk assessment, early warning systems, and accomplishment of DRRM program targets.

These results show that while most municipalities in Marinduque have the structure and plans in place, the real challenge lies in consistent and effective implementation.

Municipalities like Boac and Buenavista can serve as models for best practices, while those like Santa Cruz, Mogpog, and Torrijos may benefit from additional technical support, targeted training, and better monitoring mechanisms to strengthen their disaster preparedness efforts.

Safety, Peace, and Order

Table 3 presents the safety, peace, and order performance. Barangays garnered a "very good" rating with a passing rate 86.23. The rating indicates that barangays have consistently complied with the indicators set under this governance area. It also reflects their commitment to ensuring a secure and peaceful environment for their constituents and their practical implementation of programs and projects that address peace, order, and public safety issues.

The Barangay Anti-Drug Abuse Council (BADAC) functionality demonstrated outstanding performance. Specifically, the organization of BADAC (100), the Rehabilitation Referral Desk with a designated duty officer (99.29), house clusters with designated House Cluster Leaders (HCL) (97.16), and the BADAC Auxiliary Team (BAT) (99.29) all attained an "Outstanding" rating. The result aligns with Callahan (2007) and Gisselquist (2014), emphasizing that good governance relies on well-structured mechanisms.

In addition, 100% of barangays have an approved BADAC Plan of Action. Barangays also attained a "Good" rating for organizing at least one community-based information and education campaign activity, scoring 75.69. Meanwhile, they received a "Very Good" rating for submitting the Consolidated Information Report (CIR) to the Municipal Anti-Illegal Drugs Abuse Council (MADAC) and the Municipal PNP Unit, achieving a passing rate of 87.94. However, only 46.10% of barangays have allocated a substantial amount for anti-illegal drug initiatives, hindering drug prevention activities in barangays without such allocations in their annual budgets. Inadequate budgetary allocation remains a challenge in attaining the Seal of Good Local Governance, as emphasized by Cagas and Balacy (2022).

Barangays also received a "Poor" rating (72.34) in implementing Community-Based Interventions for Persons Who Used Drugs (PWUDs). And a "Needs Improvement" rating (54.61) in conducting BADAC monthly meetings. The results align with the findings of Monocay and Mejica (2020), which indicate that barangay-level programs often struggle with rehabilitation support despite strong enforcement efforts. Furthermore, the low rating for monthly meetings highlights that regular engagement in governance performance is essential. Brillantes (2001) Maintaining consistent engagements remains challenging for local government units (LGUs) (Brillantes, 2001).

Regarding the functionality of the Barangay Peace and Order Committee (BPOC), which plays a vital role in maintaining peace, order, and public safety, 93.62% of barangays received an "Outstanding" rating for organizing the BPOC in compliance with the minimum membership requirements set by EO No. 366. Additionally, all barangays have an approved Barangay Peace and Order and Public Safety (BPOPS) Plan (100%)

and attained an "Outstanding" rating of 92.20% in accomplishing the plan's physical and financial targets.

These findings align with Fenwick (1995), who distinguished between governance performance measures and broader effectiveness measures, suggesting that barangays have made progress in their initiatives to maintain peace, order, and public safety.

In evaluating the functionality of the Lupong Tagapamayapa, 75.89% of barangays effectively organized the Lupong Tagapamayapa, earning a "Good" rating. The attendance of Lupong Tagapamayapa members in training and seminars related to their functions received an "Outstanding" rating (95.04%), indicating that barangays prioritize capacity development for Lupon members. Additionally, 97.16% of barangays (Outstanding) maintained systematic records of cases under the Katarungang Pambarangay. Only 52.48% of barangays (Needs Improvement) conducted at least three-monthly meetings to administer Katarungang Pambarangay. Garcia et al. (2023) found similar results in their study, showing that while structures may be in place, executing programs, projects, and activities is crucial.

Barangays also performed satisfactorily in organizing and strengthening the capacities of barangay "tanods". They attained an "Outstanding" rating (99.29%) in the organization of barangay "tanods" and a "Very Good" rating (88.65%) in barangay tanods' attendance at training sessions related to their functions. Likewise, barangays performed well in implementing initiatives during health emergencies. Most barangays successfully organized their respective Barangay Health and Emergency Response Teams (BHERTs), achieving an "Outstanding" passing rate of 91.49%. Additionally, they received a "Very Good" rating (89.36%) for posting posters or tarpaulins displaying the active contact numbers of BHERT members. Finally, barangays attained a "Very Good" performance rating, with an 87.94% passing rate, for conducting at least three Barangay Road Clearing operations.

The results show that the selected barangays demonstrated strong performance in the core governance area of safety, peace, and order. Barangays exhibited high compliance in organizing essential teams and ensuring attendance at necessary training sessions. However, they struggled with allocating funds for anti-illegal drug activities and conducting regular monthly meetings for BADAC and the Lupong Tagapamayapa. Cagas and Balacy (2022) highlighted in their study that limitations in financial capability reduce the effectiveness of governance.

Further analysis of Table 3 shows varying levels of performance across the six municipalities.

Boac recorded the highest average performance score at 96.36%, making it the best-performing municipality in the area of safety, peace, and order. Boac consistently obtained perfect or near-perfect scores in almost all indicators. It fully complied with the functionality of the BADAC, BPOC, and Lupong Tagapamayapa, as well as organized and trained barangay tanods and BHERTs. Boac's high rating in organizing monthly

meetings and implementing community-based interventions for PWUDs further demonstrates its commitment to effective governance.

Gasán and Buenavista also performed well, with average scores of 89.20% and 88.64%, respectively. Like Boac, these municipalities achieved high ratings for BADAC organization, presence of rehabilitation referral desks, and peace and order plans. However, both showed relatively low performance in certain key indicators. For instance, Gasán received only 12.5% in implementing community-based interventions and 50% in conducting monthly meetings for the Katarungang Pambarangay. Buenavista also had a low score in the same areas, especially with only 30% for monthly Lupong meetings and 0% for interventions for PWUDs. These gaps suggest a need to focus more on the continuity and follow-through of programs.

In contrast, Santa Cruz and Mogpog had average scores of 80.13% and 80.11%, respectively. These municipalities struggled particularly in areas that require consistent program implementation. Santa Cruz notably scored only 11.43% for allocating a substantial amount to anti-illegal drugs initiatives and the same percentage for conducting at least one IEC campaign. Similarly, Mogpog only achieved 54.17% for several indicators such as BPOC physical and financial target accomplishment and monthly meetings for Katarungang Pambarangay. The overall performance of these municipalities indicates the presence of structure but highlights weak implementation and poor resource utilization.

Torrijos, with the lowest average score of 78.98%, showed considerable gaps in key areas. Torrijos scored only 37.5% in the conduct of monthly barangay road clearing operations, 56.25% in the attendance of barangay tanods to training, and 31.25% in the conduct of monthly KP meetings.

The performance suggests that while most municipalities have successfully established the required structures, some continue to struggle with sustaining regular activities, ensuring budgetary support, and implementing community-based programs. The disparities between Boac's high scores and those of municipalities like Santa Cruz and Torrijos highlight the need for intensified coaching, increased funding for peace and order programs, and closer monitoring from municipal and provincial levels. Strengthening barangay-level capacity and follow-through is key to improving performance across all municipalities in the Safety, Peace, and Order governance area.

Social Protection and Sensitivity

Table 4 presents the performance of the selected barangays in the essential governance area of social protection and sensitivity. Barangays garnered a "Very Good" rating with an average passing rate of 89.59%. Barangays have consistently complied with the indicators set by the SGLGB program. Barangays are also committed to ensuring that vulnerable community groups receive the necessary services. As highlighted by Barrientos and Hulme (2016), adequate social protection systems are crucial in combating poverty and fostering community resilience.

Barangays demonstrated an outstanding performance in the functionality of the Barangay Violence Against Women (VAW) Desk. They established their respective Barangay VAW Desks and designated Barangay VAW Desk Officers (98.58%). Additionally, 92.91% of Barangay VAW Desk Officers attended at least one training, while all barangays (100%) formulated and approved their Barangay Gender and Development (GAD) Plan and Budget. Furthermore, 92.20% of barangays regularly submitted monthly accomplishment reports on VAW and VAC incidents, and 96.45% maintained an updated database on VAW cases. These results support the findings of Goetz and Jenkins (2018) on how social protection measures are enhanced by gender-sensitive governance. They also align with Devereux and Sabates-Wheeler (2004), who emphasized that effective reporting strengthens social protection. However, only 71.63% of barangays accomplished more than 50% of the physical and financial targets outlined in their plans. Barangays face challenges in implementing programs, projects, and activities as planned. The findings align with Gomes et al. (2020), who highlighted that program implementation often encounters issues and setbacks due to financial limitations.

Barangays demonstrated outstanding performance in the "Access to Health and Social Welfare Services" indicator. The presence of a Barangay Health Station (BHS), the appointment of a Barangay Nutrition Scholar (BNS), and the availability of health services in the BHS all achieved an outstanding passing rate of 99.29%. And the appointment of a Barangay Health Worker (BHW) garnered a perfect passing rate of 100%. Barangays are effective in delivering health and social welfare services to their constituents. The result aligns with Osborne and Flemig (2015), who argued that decentralized governance enhances service delivery when resources are appropriately allocated.

Under the indicator of Barangay Development Council (BDC) functionality, barangays received an outstanding rating for the organization of the BDC, with its composition compliant with Section 107 of RA 7160, achieving a passing rate of 97.87%. Similarly, public hearings or barangay assemblies for public consultation attained an outstanding passing rate of 95.04%. The approval of the Barangay Development Plan (BDP) received a "Very Good" rating (85.82%). At the same time, the accomplishment of the physical and financial targets under the BDP attained a "Poor" rating (61.70%). These results support Gomes et al. (2020), who highlighted that participation does not always lead to the effective implementation of programs. He also emphasized the need for an improved monitoring mechanism.

Barangays achieved outstanding performance in implementing the Kasambahay Law indicator. 97.16% of barangays have organized their respective Kasambahay Desks with designated Kasambahay Desk Officers (KDOs). In comparison, 94.33% have maintained a Kasambahay master list.

For the functionality of the Barangay Council for the Protection of Children (BCPC), barangays achieved outstanding performance in organizing the BCPC (100.00%), approving the BCPC Annual Work and Financial Plan (97.16%), maintaining a database on children (94.33%), and updating the localized flowchart of the referral system (91.49%). However, barangays received a poor rating for the attendance of BCPC

members in at least one (1) training session (60.99%) and a low passing rate for achieving at least 50% completion or utilization of PPAs under BCPC (68.09%). These findings align with Capuno et al. (2001), who emphasized that the effectiveness of social protection programs depends on continuous capacity-building initiatives.

The mechanisms for Gender and Development (GAD) attained an outstanding passing rate of 97.87%, while the maintenance of an updated Record of Barangay Inhabitants (RBIS) received a "Very Good" rating of 87.94%.

Lastly, barangays achieved an outstanding performance in organizing the BNC (91.49%) and ensuring the presence of a Barangay Nutrition Action Plan (BNAP) (97.16%). However, they only attained a "Good" rating for accomplishing 50% of the physical and financial targets under the BNAP (79.43%) and a "Poor" rating for reducing the malnutrition rate in the barangay (60.99%). The results support Fenwick (1995), who differentiated governance outcomes from governance inputs, including structures and planning.

Further analysis of Table 4 shows significant variation among municipalities in how their barangays perform in Social Protection and Sensitivity, as measured by the Seal of Good Local Governance for Barangays (SGLGB) program.

Gasan had the highest overall performance at 96.21%, indicating that its barangays are highly compliant with SGLGB standards. The municipality showed exceptional performance in almost all indicators, particularly in health services, child protection, and gender and development mechanisms. This suggests effective coordination, strong local leadership, and adequate resource mobilization to sustain social protection programs.

Boac followed with an impressive 94.29% average. Its barangays met nearly all structural and programmatic requirements, with full marks on health-related indicators and the GAD system. However, Boac scored very low in the attendance of BCPC members in training, with only 2.5%, and in reducing malnutrition, scoring just 37.5%. These findings suggest that while the structures are in place, there is a need to strengthen program implementation and capacity-building for child protection and nutrition initiatives.

Buenavista scored 91.43%, reflecting strong performance in organizing social protection bodies like VAW desks and BCPCs. Its lowest rating was also in reducing malnutrition (10.00%) and moderate performance in utilization of PPAs and BCPC training. These scores point to a need for enhanced implementation and monitoring efforts at the barangay level.

Santa Cruz came in at 91.12%, with high performance in structural indicators but weaker implementation in several areas. For instance, only 11.43% of barangays achieved at least 50% utilization of BCPC programs, and their accomplishment of BDC and BNAP targets was similarly low. This suggests that Santa Cruz may benefit from increased training, planning support, and financial resources to improve program delivery.

Mogpog had an average score of 85.86%, falling below the other municipalities. While it met most structural indicators, its barangays recorded low performance in development planning (29.17%), BCPC utilization (50.00%), and nutrition implementation (37.50%). These scores imply that despite existing frameworks, Mogpog needs targeted interventions in execution, budgeting, and coordination.

Torrijos had the lowest performance at 72.32%, reflecting critical weaknesses across multiple areas. Although its barangays established key structures such as GAD focal points, VAW desks, and nutrition committees, implementation was poor. For example, only 25.00% of barangays met targets in the VAW plans, 12.50% in BDPs, 18.75% in BNAPs, and 50.00% in Kasambahay list maintenance. The very low attendance in BCPC training and incomplete child databases (56.25%) further point to major gaps in delivery and follow-through.

Business-Friendliness and Competitiveness

Table 5 presents the performance of the selected barangays in the essential governance area of business friendliness and competitiveness. Barangays showed an outstanding performance, with an average passing rate of 90.25%. This result indicates that barangays have met the indicators set under this governance area, demonstrating their commitment to improving business friendliness and competitiveness.

Barangays attained an outstanding rating in the enactment of a barangay tax ordinance according to Section 129 of the Local Government Code (LGC) (97.87%), the enactment of a barangay ordinance related to barangay clearance fees for business permits and locational clearance (97.16%), and the posting of a citizen's charter on the issuance of barangay clearance (94.33%). These results align with the study of Brillantes and Sonco (2005), which emphasizes that local autonomy enhances governance by allowing barangays to generate their resources.

However, the indicator on an approved resolution authorizing the Municipal Treasurer to collect fees for barangay clearance for business permits and locational clearance only attained a "Good" rating, with a passing rate of 71.63%. This finding supports Gomes et al. (2020), who emphasized that administrative challenges and issues can hinder policy implementation even when a regulatory framework is in place.

A closer look at municipal performance reveals that Boac, Gasan, and Mogpog each scored a perfect 100%, demonstrating exemplary implementation across all indicators. This reflects their strong legislative capacity and clear administrative processes. Meanwhile, Santa Cruz (79.29%), Buenavista (77.50%), and Torrijos (73.44%) scored lower, primarily due to their failure to pass the resolution authorizing the Municipal Treasurer to collect fees. Santa Cruz scored only 17.14% in this specific indicator, revealing a significant compliance gap despite performing well in other areas. Similarly, Buenavista scored only 20%, and Torrijos lagged behind in the posting of the Citizen's Charter (50%), which further pulled down its score.

Environmental Management

Table 6 presents the performance of the selected barangays in the essential governance area of environmental management. Barangays showed a "Very Good" performance with an average passing rate of 80.50%. Barangays have met several key indicators, but there are still areas for improvement in addressing environmental issues.

Under the functionality of the Barangay Ecological Solid Waste Management Committee (BESWMC), barangays attained an "Outstanding" rating in the organization of the BESWMC (99.29%) and the approval of a Solid Waste Management Program/Plan with corresponding fund allocation (98.15%). However, barangays received a "Good" rating in BESWMC members' attendance at necessary training (75.18%) and a "Needs Improvement" rating in accomplishing at least 50% of the physical or financial targets under the BESWMC plan. This finding supports the study of Andre et al. (2020), which highlights the role of effective governance structures in promoting environmental sustainability.

Barangays got a 100% passing rate in establishing a Materials Recovery Facility (MRF). Showing that barangays in Marinduque are committed to addressing environmental issues. The result aligns with the requirements of RA 9003, or the Ecological Solid Waste Management Act of 2000, which mandates barangays to set up waste recovery facilities. However, barangays received a "Needs Improvement" rating of 52.48% in enacting a Barangay Ordinance on waste segregation at source. Showing the need for stronger policy enforcement and community engagement in solid waste management efforts.

Continuing the analysis of Table 6, notable variations in performance among municipalities are seen under the Environmental Management governance area.

Gasan achieved a perfect score of 100.00%, making it the top-performing municipality in this area. Buenavista (90.00%) and Boac (88.33%) followed closely behind, also showing strong compliance with major indicators such as organizing the BESWMC and establishing a Materials Recovery Facility (MRF).

Mogpog (88.19%) also performed well overall, but it notably lagged in completing and utilizing at least 50% of the programs, projects, and activities (PPAs) under the Barangay Solid Waste Management Plan only achieving 29.17%. Meanwhile, Torrijos got a score of 79.17%, and Santa Cruz with a significantly lower performance score of 55.24%, struggled to meet several key indicators. Santa Cruz received only 17.14% for BESWMC members' attendance in training and 0.00% for program accomplishment under the SWM plan. Furthermore, it had one of the lowest ratings for enacting an ordinance on source segregation of waste, scoring only 14.29%.

Part II. Role of Stakeholders in the Implementation of the SGLGB Program in the Selected Barangays in Terms of:

Financial Administration and Sustainability

Table 7 shows the performance of stakeholders with their role in Financial Administration and Sustainability. Respondents agreed that they are effective in performing their role in financial administration, with a mean score of 3.1362.

Among the different roles, capacity building providers received the highest rating of 3.2350. Followed by financial oversight partners and technical experts (3.1913 and 3.1803). The result highlights that outside support is important to strengthen financial management. This result aligns with Andrews and Shah's (2003) argument that external factors are vital in improving governance and financial administration. The result also aligns with stakeholder theory, highlighting that participation in governance and accountability is important (Freeman et al., 2010).

Participatory budgeting contributors received a mean score of 3.1749. Inclusive governance helps balance interests and ensures accountability and transparency in financial management (Freeman et al., 2010). Ethical and moral advocates garnered a mean of 3.1366. Underscoring the role of stakeholder engagement in promoting ethical decision-making supports Freeman et al. (2010) findings that active stakeholder involvement reduces the risk of corruption within organizations.

Meanwhile, resource allocation influencers and policy advisors received lower mean both garnering 3.0929. This suggests that the impact of stakeholder on resource distribution and policy development is perceived as less effective. Stakeholders in these roles may have limited influence on key financial decisions.

Lastly, the role infrastructure investment partners received the lowest mean score of 3.0874. Respondents perceive stakeholder engagement in significant financial investments as limited. Stakeholders may contribute to funding small-scale projects; large-scale infrastructure initiatives typically rely on government funding (Osborne, 2010).

The overall results show that stakeholders have a limited impact on financial decisions. While respondents answered that the stakeholders' role in promoting financial transparency and accountability is appropriate, the effectiveness of stakeholders in financial planning and large funding projects remains minimal.

Among all the stakeholders, the MLGOOs garnered the highest mean (3.3333). This result means that MLGOOs are viewed as the most effective stakeholders in their roles within financial administration and sustainability. Their high rating reflects a strong perception of their contribution to ensuring transparency, governance, and accountability in financial practices.

Disaster Preparedness

Table 8 provides the effectiveness of stakeholders in their role in the Disaster Preparedness governance area. Stakeholders are effective on the given roles, with a grand mean of 3.1732.

Stakeholders as community coordinators received the highest mean score of 3.2350. The result supports the argument of Saeed and Kasim (2019) that communities are the first line of defence in disaster preparedness. As such, they have to be actively involved in planning and response efforts.

The role of stakeholders in assisting in community mobilization ranked second (3.2186). Stakeholder involvement is important in empowering communities. Strong collaboration between local government and stakeholders enhances community engagement. (McQuaid, 2000). Furthermore, the result supports Cornwall and Coelho (2007), who argue that community mobilization is important in improving participatory governance.

Stakeholders as interagency coordinators ranked third with a rating of 3.2131. Inter-agency coordination is important in ensuring effective local governance. (Saeed and Kasim, 2019).

Followed by stakeholders as public awareness advocates attaining a mean score of 3.2407. Respondents recognize the crucial role of stakeholders in ensuring timely and accurate information regarding disasters. Information education campaigns are important in enhancing disaster preparedness, as Saeed and Kasim (2019) highlighted in their study.

The role as policy developers ranked fifth, with a mean score of 3.1858. Comprehensive disaster preparedness and risk reduction management policies are important in providing clear guidelines for risk assessment, mitigation, and response efforts (Osborne and Flemig, 2015).

Stakeholders as first responders, logistical support providers, funding supporters and risk reduction planners all ranked in the lower middle. While respondents recognize these roles are essential, stakeholders do not actively engage directly in response efforts.

Lastly, Stakeholders research and risk analysts received the lowest rank, with a mean of 3.1327. Respondents believe this role is the least performed in disaster preparedness. The result shows a gap in using scientific approaches to disaster preparedness and there is a need to encourage barangays to partner with local research institutions and other disaster management experts to address the gap. (Saeed and Kasim, 2019)

Among all the stakeholders, the MLGOOs garnered the highest mean (3.5000). This result means that MLGOOs are viewed as the most effective stakeholders in the roles in disaster preparedness.

Safety, Peace, and Order

Table 9 presents the effectiveness of stakeholders in their role in the safety, peace, and order governance area. Respondents agreed they are effective on their roles, with a grand mean of 3.1607.

The highest-rank role, stakeholders as community watch partners got a mean score of 3.1967. Participation of people in reporting crimes contributes to maintaining a secure and safe community (Callahan, 2007).

Collaborators in social program implementation, received the second highest mean score of 3.1913. The result shows that effective governance relies on collaboration between stakeholders and government agencies to enhance peace, order, and public safety initiatives (Usman, 2023). The role community project supporters garnered the same result with mean score of 3.1913.

Accountability and human rights monitors, peace education providers, peace and order monitors and local governance supporters ranked in the lower middle. While, governance process participants, law adherence advocates and funding and logistical support providers all garnered the lowest score with 3.1366. The result shows that while the stakeholders are performing this role, their involvement may not be that strong.

The above results show the critical role of stakeholders in maintaining peace and order at the barangay level, specifically in partnership with local government units, community involvement, and their participation in discussions about safety, peace, and order.

Among all the stakeholders, the MLGOOs garnered the highest mean (3.6833). This result means that MLGOOs are viewed as the most effective stakeholders in the roles in safety, peace and order.

Social Protection and Sensitivity

Table 10 provides the effectiveness of stakeholders in their role in Social Protection and Sensitivity. Respondents are effective on the roles with a grand mean of 3.1714.

The role of stakeholders as community initiative participants received the highest mean of 3.2186. Respondents agree that stakeholders are effective in their participation in local initiatives and contribute to barangays' health and livelihood.

Abuse and neglect reporters garnered a mean of 3.2131. This result means that stakeholders help barangays track the progress of programs being implemented to ensure they benefit marginalized people. Stakeholders also ensure that they help barangays monitor and report cases involving vulnerable groups. This result aligns with Barrientos and Hulme's (2016) study, highlighting that strong oversight is needed to ensure adequate social protection.

Stakeholders collaborate with social welfare departments garnered a mean of 3.1913. Collaboration between stakeholders and government units requires effective implementation of social programs (Fiszbein & Schady, 2009). Fiszbein and Schady (2009) argued that collaboration between stakeholders and government units requires effective implementation of social programs.

Program oversight partners and awareness campaign advocates both got a mean of 3.1858. The result shows the active partnerships with local government units to ensure that social protection is the main focus of barangay policies. Further, the result shows the commitment of stakeholders in providing the community with the necessary knowledge on social awareness through information education campaigns.

The roles of stakeholder as representation advocates, social inclusion trainers, rights advocates for marginalized communities, policy enforcers for social protection all ranked in the lower middle.

The lowest-ranked role was resource allocators for social protection programs, scoring 3.1366. The result suggests that financial support from stakeholders is limited. Barangays mainly depend on their budget to finance social protection projects. Barangays needed to enhance their financial sustainability to answer key challenges in social protection (Devereux & Sabates-Wheeler, 2004).

Among all the stakeholders, the MLGOOs garnered the highest mean (3.5000). This result means that MLGOOs are viewed as the most effective stakeholders in the roles in social protection and sensitivity.

Business Friendliness and Competitiveness

Table 11 provides the effectiveness of stakeholders in performing their role in Business Friendliness and Competitiveness. Stakeholders are effective with a grand mean of 3.1383.

The role of stakeholders as economic research providers is the most performed role with a mean of 3.2186. The result shows that stakeholders gather information and find new ways to improve local businesses. Research and innovations are important in helping businesses become competitive (Ahmed & McQuaid, 2005).

Development initiatives participants come in second, garnering a mean score of 3.1858. Respondents agree that one of the stakeholders' roles is to work with local government units and other agencies to help solve economic issues and help businesses keep running.

Policy framework developers also ranked second as most performed role with a mean of 3.1858. It is important to create policies and programs that make it easier for businesses to succeed. Tonkiss (2008) highlights that good policies help businesses grow and compete better.

Stakeholders as business supporters supporting local businesses through consumption and labour got a mean rating of 3.1639. Stakeholders help the economy by buying from local businesses, and providing jobs. Ahmed and McQuaid (2005) explain that strong local support is necessary for business success.

Meanwhile, Stakeholders as policy reform advocates who advocate for policy reforms that enhance business competitiveness and financial and technical assistance providers both got a mean of 3.1257. This result means that while stakeholders help create good business policies and provide financial and technical support, there is still a need to improve these efforts.

Stakeholders as entrepreneurial capacity builders and business development service providers received a mean of 3.1202 and 3.0984 respectively. Meaning these are also important. However, there is room for improvement in how they are carried out.

The least performed roles include local investors and job creators (3.0929) and public-private partnership collaborators (3.656). This result suggests that while stakeholders help with economic growth, they do not invest as much in job creation and public-private partnerships. Ahmed and McQuaid (2005) stress that putting more money into infrastructure is necessary to help businesses grow.

Environmental Management

Table 12 provides the effectiveness of stakeholders in performing their role in the governance area of Environmental Management. Stakeholders are effective with their role with a grand mean of 3.1650.

Stakeholders as environmental reporters where stakeholders report environmental violations to authorities and environmental researchers both garnered the number one rank with a mean of 3.2077. This result shows that stakeholders help monitor and ensure environmental rules are followed. Cotler et al. (2022) also stress that stakeholders play a significant role in enforcing environmental policies. The result also shows that stakeholders conduct research, study environmental problems, and spread awareness to find solutions. The efforts of stakeholders help create policies and programs that address environmental concerns, which is important in protecting the environment (Lemos & Agrawal, 2006).

The third most performed role is the provision of environmental education and training, receiving a rating of 3.1858. This result means that teaching people about the environment is key to long-term conservation efforts, as highlighted by Cotler et al. (2022) and Lemos and Agrawal (2006).

Policy advocates for the environment scored 3.1803, showing that while stakeholders contribute to policy-making, they must be more involved in ensuring these rules are correctly followed.

Taking part in local environmental activities and conservation efforts was rated 3.1694 while providing funds and resources for environmental projects and regulation enforcers both scored 3.1530.

The role resource allocators for environmental projects and environmental partnership builders both garnered 3.1366 and environmental regulation developers with 3.1202 were rated the lowest. This result suggests that although stakeholders help implement environmental projects, they do not provide funding or get involved in large-scale projects with private companies. Stakeholders usually help by raising awareness and influencing policies rather than directly funding big environmental projects (Lemos & Agrawal, 2006).

Part III. Significant Relationship between the Role of Stakeholders and the Performance of the Barangays in the SGLGB Program

Table 13 presents the correlation between the role of stakeholders and the level of performance in the Seal of Good Local Governance for Barangays (SGLGB) program. The Department of the Interior and Local Government (DILG) exhibits a moderate positive correlation with Financial Administration ($r = 0.680$), Environmental Management ($r = 0.625$), Safety, Peace, and Order ($r = 0.534$), and Disaster Preparedness ($r = 0.404$). The result indicates that DILG's involvement has a notable impact on barangay performance in these areas. Meanwhile, Social Protection ($r = 0.376$) and Business Friendliness ($r = 0.187$) show a weak positive correlation with DILG's role.

On the other hand, the Municipal LGU and Civil Society Organizations (CSOs) show weak correlations across most core and essential areas. CSOs exhibit a weak positive correlation with Disaster Preparedness ($r = 0.324$) and Social Protection ($r = 0.196$). While their involvement in Financial Administration ($r = -0.122$) and Environmental Management ($r = -0.216$) reflects a weak negative correlation. The Municipal LGU's correlations are similarly weak, with no strong influence in any category.

The result shows that DILG plays the most significant role in improving barangay performance, particularly in Financial Administration and Environmental Management. While CSOs and the Municipal LGU have limited effects. This supports Republic Act No. 11292 or the SGLG Act, which serves as the foundation of DILG Memorandum Circular No. 2023-103. This policy designates DILG as the overall lead agency in implementing the SGLGB program. Thus, most of the roles are expected to be performed by the department being the implementing agency.

On the other hand, the performance of stakeholders on its roles shows a direct influence on how barangays perform in SGLGB base on the result of SOP No. 1 and SOP No. 2. Especially in areas that demand technical guidance, community coordination, and compliance with government standards. The effectiveness of stakeholders in Financial Administration and Sustainability reflects the support they provide through capacity building and financial oversight. High scores in these roles, especially from MLGOOs, appear to support barangays in managing their finances transparently and accountably. However, the lower ratings in roles like financial strategy and infrastructure investment

suggest that stakeholders contribute less to long-term planning and resource mobilization. This partly explain why barangays scored low in increasing local revenues and submitting financial reports that require financial guidance and capacity development.

In Disaster Preparedness, barangays demonstrated strong performance, which is mirrored by stakeholders being rated highly in community coordination, public awareness, and mobilization roles. These contributions lenabled barangays to meet the functional requirements of disaster preparedness. Such as establishing BDRRM plans and evacuation centers. However, stakeholders' limited involvement in research, risk analysis, and funding implies that while the barangays can implement basic preparedness actions, they lack the support needed for advanced risk management and innovation.

For Safety, Peace, and Order, stakeholders' strong involvement as community watch partners and collaborators in social programs reflects positively on barangay compliance with anti-drug abuse councils and peace and order plans. Yet, challenges persist in sustaining regular BADAC meetings and funding anti-drug activities, likely due to stakeholders' limited role in financial and logistical support.

In Social Protection, stakeholders are perceived as effective, particularly in participating in community initiatives and monitoring abuse cases. These roles contribute significantly to the barangays' high compliance in health services, VAW desks, and child protection mechanisms. Nonetheless, their lower engagement in policy enforcement and funding for social programs correlates with barangays' challenges in fully achieving targets in social development plans, such as the BCPC and nutrition programs.

In Business-Friendliness and Competitiveness, stakeholders were most effective as economic researchers and development participants. Their role in supporting policy development and consumption also correlates with barangays' strong compliance in local tax and permit regulations. However, minimal stakeholder roles in investing and forming partnerships may contribute to the lower barangay performance in resolutions for fee collection and public-private collaborations.

In Environmental Management, stakeholder involvement in reporting violations and conducting research aligns with barangay performance in forming committees and developing waste management plans. However, low scores in stakeholder funding and regulatory roles likely contribute to barangays' weaker compliance in ordinance enforcement and program implementation.

Stakeholder performance appears to directly affect barangay performance in the SGLGB program. Where stakeholder roles are well-executed. Such as in technical assistance, community coordination, and monitoring. Barangays tend to show stronger compliance and outcomes. However, gaps in long-term investment, policy development, and strategic planning from stakeholders hinder barangays from excelling in areas that require sustained support. Strengthening these underperformed stakeholder roles could significantly enhance barangay governance and help close performance gaps.

Part IV. Challenges that Affect the Performance of Selected Barangays in the SGLGB program and the Role of Stakeholders

Challenges that affect the performance of selected barangays in the SGLGB program

Table 14 provides the respondents' agreement level on the challenges that affect the performance of selected barangays in the SGLGB program. Respondents generally agree on their roles with a grand mean of 3.0636.

The biggest challenge based on the respondents is the difficulty due to inadequate financial resources for implementing SGLGB Program activities, which had a mean of 3.1481. Most of the barangays struggle to get enough funding support for the implementation of their programs, projects, and activities (PPAs). Financial independence is important for the barangays to function well, as Brillantes and Sonco (2005) highlighted in their study.

Lack of community awareness and engagement in SGLGB Program initiatives is ranked second with a score of 3.0957. Residents do not fully understand the SGLGB program or take part in its activities. Non-participation makes it harder for barangays to succeed. The support of the community is important to implement projects successfully. Cornwall and Coelho (2007) highlighted in their study that the success of implementing local projects depends on the participation of people.

Lack of trained personnel to manage and execute the SGLGB Program effectively and poor infrastructure in barangays hampers the achievement of SGLGB Program goals, both coming in third with a mean of 3.0802. Most respondents agree that barangays lack skilled personnel and proper facilities, making it difficult to run programs, projects, and activities efficiently. Training local government workers is key to improving government services (Osborne and Flemig, 2015).

Disaster preparedness and management issues also ranked high, with a mean of 3.0741, which means that barangays are not fully ready to handle disasters. As highlighted by Saeed and Kasim (2019), local communities need better planning and preparation to handle disasters effectively.

Other challenges include political interference, with a mean of 3.0617, and conflicts between barangay officials and residents, with a mean of 3.0556, which can slow down decision-making and program implementation. Barangays also struggle with limited access to important information and resources, getting a mean of 3.0494 and slow government processes and paperwork with 3.0309.

Insufficient support from local government units attains the lowest ranking with a mean of 2.9599. Respondents see the lack of support from LGU as the least pressing challenge. While it is still considered a challenge, barangays rely more on their ways to carry out the SGLGB program.

The result shows that barangays face several challenges in meeting the requirements of the SGLGB program. The biggest issue is the lack of funding. Many people are also unaware of the program and do not actively participate. The lack of training and poor infrastructure also affect the effective implementation of PPAs.

Barangays in Marinduque need better financial support and additional training to capacitate their personnel and enhance the awareness of the community. Solving the issues would help Barangays pass the indicators under the SGLGB program.

Challenges that affect the role of stakeholders in the SGLGB program

Table 15 provides the respondents' level of agreement on the challenges that affect the role of stakeholders in the SGLGB program. Respondents generally agree on their roles with a grand mean of 3.0265.

The biggest challenge based on the respondents is the lack of understanding of the requirements and processes of the SGLGB Program, which has the highest rating of 3.0741. Most stakeholders do not know the program guidelines. Capacity building plays a crucial role in understanding the program requirements and processes. Equipping stakeholders with the necessary knowledge and skills would help them perform better (Osborne and Flemig, 2015). Similarly, as stressed by Andrews and Shah (2003), continuous learning helps strengthen financial management and decision-making in local governance.

Mobilizing community support ranks second as perceived by the respondents, with a rating of 3.0679. One of the stakeholders' issues is the mobilization of the community to support the initiatives for the SGLGB program. Community support is essential to attain good local governance, as Cornwall and Coelho (2007) highlighted.

Another significant issue is the lack of training and capacity-building opportunities for stakeholders involved in the SGLGB Program (3.0401). Stakeholders find it challenging to contribute with the help of the initiatives of SGLGB without the proper skills and knowledge about the program. Training and capacity development activities are the key to improving service delivery (Osborne and Flemig, 2015).

Other challenges include the provision of constructive feedback for the improvement of the SGLGB Program with 3.0370. Political or personal conflicts among stakeholders and barangay officials with a rating of 3.0340. Establishing effective communication with barangay officials with 3.0154 and insufficient resources allocated to stakeholders with 3.0093. Limited access to information and lack of coordination among stakeholders got a rating of 3.0031 and 2.9938, respectively. While these challenges are within the middle of the ranking, respondents still see this as one of the issues that must be addressed to implement the SGLGB program and other barangay programs effectively.

The lowest-rated challenge is that stakeholders are often not included in the decision-making processes related to the SGLGB Program.

Proactive steps must be taken to improve barangay compliance with the SGLGB program. The provision of capacity-building initiatives would help stakeholders gain the necessary skills and knowledge and actively contribute to the barangays' governance initiatives (Osborne and Flemig, 2015).

Community engagement efforts must also be strengthened to raise awareness about the program and encourage the people to participate and become active in the governance efforts of barangays. Community awareness could be attained through information education campaigns and strengthened partnerships with civil society organizations (Cornwall & Coelho, 2007).

Further, improving communication will solve conflicts. Creating open discussions where the stakeholders can share their concerns and feedback will help barangays and stakeholders work better and make smarter decisions.

Part V. Strategies to Improve the Performance of Barangays in the SGLGB Program

DILG initiated strategies to improve the performance of barangays in the SGLGB program

Table 16 provides the list of strategies to improve the performance of barangays in SGLGB that could be initiated by DILG as perceived by the respondents.

The most recommended strategy is to conduct workshops for barangay officials on governance, financial management, and accountability, with 89.30% of respondents voting for it. This shows that respondents believe barangay leaders need more guidance in managing their financial affairs. The study of Osborne and Flemig (2015) and Andrews and Shah (2003) highlight that training government workers results in better services, decreased corruption, and better financial management.

The second most suggested strategy is creating a digital platform for real-time monitoring of barangay performance and SGLGB compliance with 74.90%. The data shows the need for the Department of the Interior and Local Government to develop a system to help barangays track their performance based on the SGLGB indicators. Using technology improves accountability and transparency and makes government services more efficient, as Osborne and Flemig (2015) highlighted.

Another recommended strategy is to develop a training program for barangay officials with 74.60%. The idea highlights the importance of training barangay officials and employees to attain good governance.

Meanwhile, 72.20% of the respondents also believe conducting an information education campaign to educate communities about the SGLGB program would help barangays. When people understand the programs being implemented by the government, they are more likely to take the initiative to provide support (Cornwall & Coelho, 2007).

Further, the facilitation of workshops for barangays to share best practices and collaborate on joint projects got 69.70%. Respondents agree that this strategy would help barangays attain the SGLGB program. Learning from other successes would strengthen barangays' local governance, as McQuaid (2000) pointed out.

Establishing a support system and comprehensive guide (60.20%), a benchmarking system (58.70%), and collaboration with states and universities to conduct research (50.50%) all got lower scores. This result shows that barangays may focus more on immediate results than on the long-term. However, research helps create better policies that can improve governance in the long run, as Cotler et al. (2022) pointed out.

Barangay initiated strategies to improve the performance of barangays in the SGLGB program

Table 17 provides the list of strategies to improve the performance of barangays in SGLGB that could be initiated by Barangay LGU as perceived by the respondents.

The most recommended strategy is creating an SGLGB team that would spearhead the monitoring of compliances in the SGLGB program, with 77.50% of respondents voting for it. Having a dedicated team ensures that barangays can monitor their performance and meet the standards set by the program. According to Osborne and Flemig (2015), forming a specific team helps improve efficiency and accountability in local governance.

The second most recommended step is holding monthly meetings with 72.00% to discuss the SGLGB program. Regular discussions will help barangay officials stay updated and address any problems quickly. Cornwall and Coelho (2007) explain that ongoing conversations among community members and leaders strengthen governance.

The third strategy is organizing quarterly forums with a vote of 64.60% where residents can give feedback and share their concerns. Respondents believe that the community should be involved more in barangay governance. McQuaid (2000) highlights that people trust their leaders and work together better when involved.

Another important strategy is creating a barangay performance improvement plan based on feedback and audit results with 63.70%. Barangays should regularly check their progress and find ways to improve. Reviewing the previous performance and using the data to guide decisions can lead to better policies and projects Andrews and Shah (2003).

Other suggested ideas include working and collaborating with groups and organizations with 59.70% to gain additional support for barangay projects, regularly reviewing barangay performance (54.70%), and monitoring how resources are used (52.60%) to ensure proper funds allocation. 51.10% of respondents suggested initiating community-driven projects, while 49.80% recommended forming councils with neighboring barangays. Installing suggestion boxes and online forms to encourage resident feedback received 48.90% support. Although these strategies promote

community involvement, they were ranked lower. Respondents regard other strategies as more urgent and necessary.

Part VI. Possible Policy Interventions that can be Formulated to Address the Gap Identified in the Study

Based on the results of the study, the researcher recommended an intervention that will address the gaps identified in the study. The researcher recommends that the Department of the Interior and Local Government (DILG) must take a more proactive role in strengthening the performance of barangays in the Seal of Good Local Governance for Barangays (SGLGB) program. DILG may provide technical assistance and institutionalize governance reforms. DILG may also issue a DILG Memorandum Circular titled "Institutionalizing DILG Support Mechanisms for Strengthening Barangay Governance in the SGLGB Program." The policy can focus on mandating DILG Provincial and Field Offices to provide direct technical support to barangays. It may also establish a Barangay Governance Support Unit to assist barangays in preparing Means of Verification (MOVs) and compliance with reports. DILG may conduct Quarterly performance audits led by DILG provincial offices to assess governance improvements and compliance gaps. Strengthening the barangay coaching program through Municipal Local Government Operations Officers (MLGOOs) will also ensure that barangays receive structured training and real-time feedback on their performance.

DILG may track barangay compliance in real-time and enhance oversight and monitoring. Conducting random governance audits will help verify the accuracy of MOV submissions and detect compliance issues. Additionally, MLGOOs may submit quarterly progress reports on barangay performance. Allowing DILG to provide timely interventions when needed.

DILG may develop a Digital Monitoring and Performance Tracking System to improve barangay governance. Establishing a digital dashboard will allow DILG to track barangay compliance in real time. Develop a training program focused on enhancing the capacity of barangays. DILG may also implement an information education campaign to educate communities about the SGLGB program. Additionally, they may facilitate sharing best practices among barangays.

On the other hand, barangays should ensure compliance with SGLGB indicators by creating an SGLGB Compliance Team. The team would monitor the adherence to the program requirements. Barangays must also conduct regular monthly meetings to discuss compliance and challenges. Additionally, they should organize quarterly community forums. Barangays must also develop a performance improvement plan based on feedback and audit findings.

Conclusions

This study assessed the role of stakeholders and performance of selected barangays in Marinduque in implementing the Seal of Good Local Governance for

Barangays (SGLGB) program. The findings highlight that while barangays generally performed well in most SGLGB areas, there remain critical challenges in Environmental Management, Financial Administration, and stakeholder engagement, which require immediate attention.

The Department of the Interior and Local Government (DILG) as its implementer plays the most significant role in improving barangay performance, particularly in Financial Administration, Environmental Management, Safety, Peace and Order, and Disaster Preparedness. In contrast, Municipal LGUs and Civil Society Organizations (CSOs) have limited influence, with CSOs even showing negative correlations in some governance areas.

Key challenges identified include insufficient financial resources, limited community awareness, lack of trained personnel, and poor infrastructure. Addressing these barriers through structured training, digital monitoring platforms, and targeted interventions will be crucial to sustaining governance improvements.

The study also identified effective strategies initiated by both DILG and barangays. DILG initiated workshops on governance, financial management, and accountability were found to be the most impactful interventions, along with digital monitoring platforms and public awareness campaigns. Meanwhile, barangay-initiated initiatives such as forming an SGLGB team, holding regular compliance meetings, and conducting community engagement forums were key efforts to enhance governance at the local level.

Recommendations

The following are hereby recommended based on the findings of the study.

To the Department of the Interior and Local Government

- Conduct workshops for barangay officials on governance, financial management, and accountability.
- Establish an integrated, user-friendly digital platform that allows barangays to track their SGLGB compliance in real time, submit reports, and receive feedback from higher-level authorities to enhance transparency and efficiency in governance.
- Design and implement a standard training curriculum for barangay officials.
- Establish a formal recognition system to acknowledge and reward active stakeholders.
- Create clear and accessible guides outlining best practices for stakeholder involvement in the SGLGB program.
- Regularly evaluate the level of stakeholder participation in barangay governance and provide feedback.

To the Sangguniang Barangays

- Set up an SGLGB committee within the barangay council to manage the program's implementation and documentation and ensure compliance.
- Hold monthly meetings to review compliance status, discuss updates on governance performance, and identify areas that require Improvement.
- Facilitate open quarterly forums where stakeholders can discuss governance issues and provide suggestions.
- Create a communication plan to enhance the involvement of stakeholders.
- Form an advisory committee composed of CSOs, the private sector, and other key stakeholders.
- Develop a training program to educate stakeholders on the specifics of the SGLGB program.

To Future Researchers

- Utilize this study as a benchmark for evaluating barangay performance in the SGLGB program across different provinces.
- Conduct a more in-depth study focusing on the barangay implementation system and decision-making processes.
- Study the effect of the role of stakeholders to the performance of barangays in the SGLGB program.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researcher of this study affirms full compliance with ethical standards throughout the conduct of the research. Informed consent was duly obtained from all respondents prior to their participation. They were clearly informed of the purpose of the study, their role, and their right to voluntarily participate or withdraw from the study at any stage without any consequence. The anonymity and confidentiality of all participants were strictly maintained; no identifying information was collected or disclosed in the reporting of results.

The researcher declares that there was no conflict of interest involved in the conduct of the study. The study was conducted impartially, and all findings were analyzed and interpreted objectively and without bias. Plagiarism was strictly avoided by properly citing all sources and references used in the research. The results of the study were used exclusively for academic and research purposes, with the intention of contributing to the improvement of local governance practices.

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